

INFLUENCE OF CONTINUOUS CARBONIZATION ON THE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PAN-BASED CARBON FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The properties of six kinds of polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibers, which had been pre-carbonized from 300° to 550° C respectively during two-stage continuous carbonization, were measured. The effect of pre-carbonization (300-550° C) on the final properties and microstructure of carbon fibers was measured. Experimental results using a X-ray diffractometer indicated the presence of several less ordered structure at 2Θ from 5 to 18° in the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers. This study found that the pre-carbonization process affects strongly the microstructure of the resulting carbon fibers. The results of this study also showed that a suitable pre-carbonization was very conducive to improvement in tensile strength or in Young's modulus of the final carbon fibers. When the final carbon fiber was pre-carbonized at 300 and 550° C, respectively, these fibers had a higher tensile strength and better Young's modulus than carbon fibers which were precarbonized at other conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber is now effectively used as a reinforcing component in the preparation of light weight composite materials because of its high strength, high elastic modulus, and low density. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and its copolymers have been found to be the most suitable precursors for making high-performance carbon fibers. The mechanical properties of the final carbon fibers depend largely on the nature of precursor fibers and various process parameters applied both on stabilization[1-3] and on carbonization[4].

Our previous studies[5-8] presented the results of the modified PAN fibers which produced high-performance carbon fibers. In this study, the authors report the effect of pre-carbonization during the two-stage continuous carbonization process on the final properties of carbon fibers. The progression of pre-carbonization and carbonization was monitored through measurements of density, elemental composition, mechanical properties, and the stacking height of the carbon layer plane (Lc).

EXPERIMENTAL

Courtelles PAN precursor (Courtaulds Ltd., U.K.), containing 6% methyl acrylate and 1% (itaconic) acid copolymer, has been used for the present studies. Each single tow of Courtelles fiber contains 6000 strands of 1.1 denier monofilament. The precursor was stabilized and carbonized by means of a continuous process, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows the continuous process comprising three furnaces in our laboratory, one for stabilization, one for pre-carbonization, one for carbonization. The stabilization furnace was divided into four zones (one meter per zone) set at different temperature regions, 190, 230, 230, and 230 °C. Two sets of differential speed rollers -- feed rollers and pinch rollers -- were located at the front and rear of the furnace, respectively, as shown in Figure 1. A variable feed roller speed was used to control the speeds of fibers entering zone 1, and a variable pinch roller speed was applied to remove fibers from zone 4. In this study, the feed rollers and pinch rollers were controlled at the same speed. PAN fibers passed through the furnace in 2.25 hours.

The pre-carbonization component of two-stage continuous carbonization process was carried out by passing the stabilized fibers through a ceramic reaction tube at temperatures ranging from 300 to 550 °C, increased at 50 °C intervals in the first oven, and then passing these fibers through the second oven, which was set at 1300 °C, as shown in Figure 1. The length of each oven was 1 meter. The speed of the take-up rollers and the pinch rollers was also the same through this two-stage process. The stabilized fibers took 30 min to pass through each of the two ovens for a total time of 60 min. An oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere was continuously passed over both ends of each furnace to maintain an inert atmosphere.

A MAC X-ray diffractometer, providing Ni-filtered Cu K_{α} radiation, was used to measure the crystalline related properties of the sample.

The mechanical properties of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers were measured using an Instron tensile-testing machine at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min and a load cell of 20 g with a testing length of 2.5 cm for all fibers. Density was measured at 25 °C according to the density gradient column method.

Figure 1 A schematic drawing showing the processing of carbon fibers from PAN fibers using continuous stabilization and two-stage carbonization.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A variation in dimension of the fiber is induced due to coalescence and condensation of molecular chains. Figure 2 shows the variation in diameter of pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers according to temperature during pre-carbonization. Diameter of the pre-carbonized fibers decreased very rapidly with an increase in the pre-carbonization temperature. This was due to the evolution of gas and the condensation of the molecular chains of stabilized fiber, which led to the formation of carbon basal planes. These reactions also promoted the crosslinking of ladder polymer and led to the repacking of the structure in the pre-carbonized fibers.

Table 1 gives the results of carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen content analysis of pre-carbonized fibers after the pre-carbonization process. During pre-carbonization, the carbon content increased and nitrogen and oxygen contents decreased. However, the variation of the nitrogen content showed a different behavior. The nitrogen content decreased with the pre-carbonization temperature increased from 300 to 400 °C. Thereafter, the nitrogen content increased from 400 to 500 °C. Above the pre-carbonization temperature of 500 °C, the nitrogen content decreased again with each step of pre-carbonization temperature increase. With processing wherein pre-carbonization temperatures ranged from 400 to 500 °C, the carbon content increased and the oxygen content decreased very slowly, but the nitrogen content showed a sudden increase during this pre-carbonization stage. This indicates that the higher pre-carbonization temperatures broke down the molecular structure of ladder polymers and promoted the evolution of CH₄ and H₂ from this breakdown. The elimination of noncarbon species led to the lengthening and broadening of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers. The resulting compaction and loss of mass led to the decrease in the diameter of the pre-carbonized fibers.

The variation in density of the pre-carbonized fibers and the resulting carbon fibers as a function of the pre-carbonization temperature are plotted in Figure 3. The density of pre-carbonized fibers increased with the increase in pre-carbonization temperature. This is due to the formation of carbon basal planes in the fiber during carbonization. The results of Table 2 showed the strong effect of the gas evolution and the resulting structural rearrangement on the pre-carbonized fibers. The mean layer planes (Lc/d) of the pre-carbonized fibers increased along with pre-carbonization temperature from 300 to 450 °C. This finding suggested that gas evolution, due to significant aromatization and crosslinking of ladder polymers, led in turn to the layer planes being repacked in the fibers. However, the layer plane decrease was followed by an increase above 500 °C. We had earlier observed this very unusual variation in the mean layer planes of carbon fibers during the carbonization process with both batch carbonization and the continuous carbonization process[9].

The effect of the pre-carbonization process on the microstructural parameters of the resulting carbon fibers is shown in Table 3. The variation in the stacking height of layer planes (Lc) and the mean layer planes (Lc/d) of the final carbon fibers look like those of the pre-carbonized fibers. This indicates that the texture of pre-carbonized

Table 1 Carbon, nitrogen and oxygen content (wt%) of pre-carbonized fibers after the pre-carbonization process

Elemental content (wt%)	Pre-carbonization temperature (°C)								
	300	350	400	450	500	550	600	650	700
Carbon	56.8	58.0	62.0	62.8	64.1	65.7	67.2	68.9	70.6
Nitrogen	18.9	18.4	18.2	19.1	19.2	18.9	18.8	18.2	17.8
Oxygen	20.1	19.7	15.4	14.8	13.7	12.6	11.5	10.6	9.6

Table 2 Variation in d spacing and stacking height (Lc) of layer planes of pre-carbonized fibers during the pre-carbonization process

	Pre-carbonization temperature (°C)							
	300	350	450	500	550	600	700	
d spacing (nm)	0.353	0.3493	0.3631	0.3559	0.3690	0.3653	0.3596	
Lc, (nm)	1.201	1.380	1.693	1.559	1.518	1.515	1.487	
Lc/d	3.39	3.95	4.66	4.38	4.11	4.15	4.14	

Table 3 Effect of pre-carbonization on d spacing and stacking height of layer planes of final carbon fibers

	Pre-carbonization temperature (°C)						
	300	350	400	450	500	550	
d spacing (nm)	0.3628	0.361	0.3648	0.3597	0.3591	0.3621	
Stacking height, Lc, (nm)	1.721	1.667	1.630	1.761	1.734	1.699	
Lc/d	4.74	4.63	4.47	4.90	4.83	4.69	

Figure 3 Density of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (◻) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

Figure 2 Diameter of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (◻) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

fiber affects the texture of the final carbon fibers. However, carbon fibers developed with pre-carbonization temperatures ranging from 450-550 °C had higher mean layer planes (Lc/d) than those fibers developed from 300 to 400 °C.

Figure 4 shows the X-ray diffractograms of the pre-carbonized fibers and the resultant carbon fibers. We found a broad weak reflection peak near (002) reflection, which appear in all pre-carbonized fibers and all final samples. The intensity of this peak in all samples was very weak and broad at 2θ ranging from 15° to 20° during pre-carbonization and carbonization. However, the intensity of this peak in the pre-carbonized samples were higher than that of the final carbon fibers.

Figure 5 shows the result when the fibers were rotated 90° to bring the X-ray beam parallel to the fiber axis. This view showed several broad peaks and several small but sharp peaks before the (002) reflection. As shown in Figure 5(a), the fiber which was precarbonized at 300 °C showed two sharp but small peaks at 9° and 13°, respectively, and two weak but broad peaks between 5-12° and 14-18°, respectively. When the sample was precarbonized at 350 °C, the intensity of these peaks increased remarkably, as shown in Figure 5(b). When the pre-carbonization temperature exceeded 350 °C, the intensity of these peaks became weak and mixed together. They exhibited a weak and broad peak from 8 to 18°, as shown in Figure 5(c). The intensity of this weak and broad peak decreased with increasing pre-carbonization temperatures.

The final carbon fiber developed with a pre-carbonization temperature of 300 °C also showed two small but sharp peaks at 9° and 13°, and a small but broad peak at 14-18°, as shown in Figure 5(d). However, the carbon fiber developed with a pre-carbonization temperature of 350 °C showed an unusual pattern, as shown in Figure 5(e). This pattern resembled the pattern of the pre-carbonized fiber, which was shown in Figure 5(b). The intensities of these peaks, between 5° and 18°, were higher for the final carbon fiber than for the pre-carbonized fiber. Above this pre-carbonization temperature, all carbon fibers showed a small peak appearing from 12° to 18°, as shown in Figure 5(f).

In this article, when the pre-carbonized fibers were pre-carbonized at 300 and 350 °C, we found several peaks in the X-ray diffraction pattern, as shown previously Figure 5. This indicated that the pre-carbonization process broke down the molecular chain and promoted condensation reactions between ladder polymers, resulting in broad heterocyclic structures. At these temperatures, a number of unknown structures having different d spacing between two layers were formed. Especially when stabilized fibers were pre-carbonized at 350 °C, these structures formed in remarkable quantities. Above 400 °C, the high temperature promoted the evolution of gas and formed the primitive graphite structures. The heat-treatment also promoted the degradation of these unknown structures. Therefore, these structures mixed together and formed a small and broad peak appearing in the X-ray diffraction profile, as shown

Figure 4 X-ray diffractograms of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers: (a) pre-carbonized at 450°C; (b) pre-carbonized at 500°C; (c) pre-carbonized at 350°C, and then carbonized up to 1300°C; (d) pre-carbonized at 700°C, and then carbonized up to 1300°C.

Figure 5 X-ray diffractograms of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers (X-ray beam parallel to the fiber axis): (a) pre-carbonized at 300°C; (b) pre-carbonized at 350°C; (c) pre-carbonized at 500°C; (d) pre-carbonized at 300°C, and then carbonized up to 1300°C; (e) pre-carbonized at 350°C, and then carbonized up to 1300°C; (f) pre-carbonized at 500°C, and then carbonized up to 1300°C.

in Figure 5(c). This indicates that the structures which appear at 2θ ranging from 15° to 20° for normal to fiber axis and at 2θ ranging from 5° to 18° for parallel to fiber axis were due to gas evolution, and link together during pre-carbonization. Some of those linked structures were parallel to the fiber axis. During pre-carbonization, these

structures showed increasing degradation with increases in pre-carbonization temperature. Therefore, the intensity of these peaks decreased when the pre-carbonization temperature increased.

The results of the effect of pre-carbonization on the Young's modulus of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers during the two-stage continuous carbonization process are plotted in Figure 6. Watt and his coworkers[14] found that the temperature range from 500 ° to 1000 °C induced an intermolecular reaction, evolving HCN and N₂ and leading to the lengthening and broadening of carbon basal planes from ladder polymers. This explains the increase of modulus of the pre-carbonized fibers with increase in the pre-carbonization temperature in the current study. For the final carbon fibers, the Young's modulus decreased slowly with increased pre-carbonization temperatures from 300 ° to 450 °C, and then increased slowly above this temperature. This study showed a very interesting phenomenon. This indicated that the modulus of the final carbon fibers developed under lower pre-carbonization temperatures was higher than that of fibers developed under higher pre-carbonization temperatures.

The progression of the variation in tensile strength of the pre-carbonized fibers and the final carbon fibers are plotted as a function of pre-carbonization temperature in Figure 7. The tensile strength of the pre-carbonized fibers increased linearly with an increase in the pre-carbonization temperature above 500 °C. Raising the temperature above 450 °C promoted the formation of longer and broader carbon basal planes, which led to progressively increasing tensile strength. It was interesting to note that when the pre-carbonized fibers were carbonized at 1300 °C to develop the final carbon fibers, tensile strength tests on the final carbon fibers showed unexpected results. When the stabilized fiber was pre-carbonized at 300 ° and 550 °C, respectively, the final carbon fibers developed from these samples had a stronger tensile strength than other carbon fibers. The reason for this is still unclear at this point. This study showed that optimization of the pre-carbonization process improves the tensile strength of the final carbon fibers.

Figure 6 Modulus of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

Figure 7 Tensile strength of pre-carbonized fibers and carbon fibers as a function of pre-carbonization temperature: (□) pre-carbonized fibers; (○) carbon fibers.

Acknowledgements

Professor Ko would like to thank Mr Ching-Li Kuo for his help in lab. Professor Ko also is especially grateful to the National Science Council of the Republic of China for its financial support of this project (No: NSC 81-0405-E035-04).

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